

The Fruit Flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Kurdistan Province, with New Records for Iranian Fauna

S. Mohamadzade Namin

Department of Plant Protection
Faculty of Agriculture
Islamic Azad University, Varamin-Pishva Branch, Varamin, Iran.

E-mail: mohamadzade@iauvaramin.ac.ir

J. Nozari

Department of Plant Protection
Faculty of Agriculture
University of Tehran, Karaj, Iran.

E-mail: nozari@ut.ac.ir

Mohamadzade Namin S. & Nozari J. The fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in Kurdistan Province, with new records for Iranian fauna.

Summary. During studies on tephritid flies fauna in Kurdistan Province (Iran) in 2009–2010, 33 species of 16 genera are found to occur in this region. *Tephritis mesopotamica*, *Tephritis pulchra*, *Urophora cuspidata*, *U. quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* and *U. tenuis* are recorded for the first time for Iranian fauna. In addition, 8 host plants are reported as a new host plant for tephritid flies.

Key words: Diptera, Tephritidae, fruit flies, Iran, new records.

Мохамадзаде-Намин С. и Нозари Дж. Мухи-пестрокрылки (Diptera: Tephritidae) провинции Курдистан, с новыми находками для фауны Ирана. Резюме. В ходе изучения мух-пестрокрылок фауны провинции Курдистан (Иран) в 2009–2010 гг., установлено, что в районе исследований встречаются 33 вида из 16 родов. Впервые для фауны Ирана отмечены *Tephritis mesopotamica*, *Tephritis pulchra*, *Urophora cuspidata*, *U. quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* и *U. tenuis*. Кроме того, впервые в качестве кормовых растений пестрокрылок указаны 8 видов растений.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, мухи-пестрокрылки, Иран, новые находки.

Мохамадзаде-Намин С. і Нозарі Дж. Мухи-осетниці (Diptera: Tephritidae) провінції Курдистан, з новими знахідками для фауни Ірану. Резюме. В ході вивчення мух-осетниць фауни провінції Курдистан (Іран) у 2009–2010 гг., встановлено, що в районі досліджень зустрічаються 33 види з 16 родів. Вперше для фауни Ірану відмічено *Tephritis mesopotamica*, *Tephritis pulchra*, *Urophora cuspidata*, *U. quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* та *U. tenuis*. Крім того, вперше в якості кормових рослин осетниць наведено 8 видів рослин.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Tephritidae, мухи-осетниці, Іран, нові знахідки.

Introduction

With about 4500 species, the family Tephritidae is one of the largest families of acalyprate Diptera. Most species are phytophagous and cause economical damage to agricultural crops and some of them effectively used in biological control programs against weeds (White & Elson-Harris, 1992).

Kurdistan Province is located in North West of Iran near Iraq border with about 29,000 km². Before this study, little information was available on the tephritid flies of this region. Three species have been known up to date from

Kurdistan Province: *Goniurellia persignata* Freidberg (Mohamadzade, Nozari & Rasouljan, 2010 b), *Sphenella marginata* (Fallén) (Mohamadzade & Nozari, in press) and *Terellia korneyevorum* Mohamadzade Namin & Nozari (Mohamadzade, Nozari & Najarpour, 2011).

Material and methods

Materials are collected by standard sweeping net and rearing from flower heads of asteraceous plants. Species were identified with the keys by Hendel (1927), Freidberg & Kugler (1989), Merz (1994), Korneyev & White (1999) and White (1989).

All the material collected by first author and is deposited in the insect collection of Jalal Afshar Zoological Museum (JAZM) and first author's personal collection (SMNC).

Species recorded in Iran for the first time are marked with asterisks (*).

Results

In this study, thirty-one species from fifteen genera were collected in Kurdistan Province. *Tephritis mesopotamica* Korneyev & Dirlbek, *Tephritis pulchra* (Loew), *Urophora cuspidata* (Meigen), *U. quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* (Meigen) and *U. tenuis* Becker are recorded for the first time for Iranian fauna and all species are new for this region. In addition, 8 host plants are reported as a new host plant for tephritid flies. *Centaurea aggregata* is a new host plant for *Urophora affinis* Frauenfeld and *Urophora quadrifasciata quadrifasciata*; *Cousinia sanandajensis* is a new host plant for *Urophora tenuior* Hendel; *Cosmos bipinnatus*, *Centaurea amadanensis*, *C. aucheri*, *C. leuzeoides* and *C. nemecii* are new hosts for *Acanthiophilus helianthi* Rossi; and *Centaurea amadanensis* and *Lactuca serriola* are new hosts for *Terellia colon* (Meigen) and *Campiglossa producta* Loew respectively.

The subfamilies, tribes, genera and species are listed in alphabetic order. Detailed morphological descriptions are not given. For further information, refer to the works of Hendel (1927), White (1988), Freidberg & Kugler (1989), White & Elson-Harris (1992), Merz (1994) and Korneyev & White (1999).

List of species

Subfamily Dacinae

Tribe Dacini

Dacus ciliatus Loew, 1862

White & Elson-Harris, 1992.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Sanandaj, 30km to Kamyaran, 1440 m, N: 34°58.385, E: 46°59.149, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. Many species of Cucurbitaceae (White & Elson-Harris, 1992).

Distribution. Iran: Hormozgan, Markazi, Esfahan, Tehran, Khorasan Razavi (Parchami Araghi, 1995; Behdad, 2003; Gilasian, 2007; Haji Ghorbani, 2010); Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Madagascar, Mauritius, Reunion, Egypt and Israel (Norrbon *et al.* 1999).

Subfamily Trypetinae

Tribe Carpomyini

Carpomya vesuviana Costa, 1854

Hendel, 1927.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Sanandaj, 30km to Kamyaran, 1440 m, N: 34°58.385, E: 46°59.149, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. *Ziziphus* spp. (Behdad, 1988)

Distribution. Iran: Gilan, Hormozgan, Tehran (Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulani, 2010a); Italy, Bosnia, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tadjikistan, Pakistan, India, UAE and Thailand (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Rhagoletis cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Hendel, 1927; Rikhter, 1988; Korneyev & Merz, 1997.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Sanandaj, 30 km to Kamyaran, 1440 m, N: 34°58.385, E: 46°59.149, swept from cherry, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. *Prunus* spp. and *Lonicera* spp. (White & Elson-Harris, 1992; Merz, 1994).

Distribution. Iran: N., S., W. and E. (Afshar, 1937); Europe, Russia, Kazakhstan and Georgia (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Subfamily Tephritinae

Tribe Myopitini

Urophora affinis (Frauenfeld, 1857) (Fig. 1)

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 8 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea aggregata* (new host plant), date of collecting: 20.VI.2010, date of exit: 25-30.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Korneyev & White, 2000).

Distribution. Iran: Mazandaran (Dirlbek & Dirlbekova, 1974); from France to Russia and North America (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Fig. 1. *Urophora affinis*, wing.

Urophora cuspidata (Meigen, 1826)* (Figs. 2 & 7)

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 3 ♀, Saral, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea* sp., date of collecting: 18.VI.2010, date of exit: 20-22.IV.2011.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Korneyev & White, 1999).

Distribution. North and Central Europe to West Siberia and Caucasus (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999); Iran (**new record**).

Diagnosis. Wing with 4 black crossbands. Preapical and apical crossbands connected in anterior margin of the wing. Subbasal crossband not extending to posterior margin of the wing (Fig. 2). Mesonotal scutum covered with gray microtomentum. Femora and antennae yellow. Aculeus tip as in Fig. 7.

Fig. 2. *Urophora cuspidata*, wing.

***Urophora pauperata* (Zaitzev, 1945) (Fig. 3)**

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 3 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, Kurdistan province, 2200 m, swept from flower heads of *Centaurea behen* (possible host plant), 6.VI.2010; 1 ♀, Hezar Kamian, 1920 m, 7.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Korneyev & White, 2000).

Distribution. Iran: West Azerbaijan (Karimpoor, 2006); Georgia and Turkey (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999).

Remark: *U. pauperata* is similar to *U. affinis* in its wing pattern with 3 widely separated crossbands (Fig. 3), differing in body length (5-5.2mm in *U. pauperata* and 3-3.2mm in *U. affinis*) and different host plants (*Centaurea (Calcitrapa)* spp. in *U. pauperata* and *Centaurea (Acrolophus)* and *C. (Phalolepis)* in *U. affinis*).

Fig. 3. *Urophora pauperata*, wing.***Urophora quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* (Meigen, 1826)* (Figs. 4 & 6)**

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 5 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, swept from flower heads of *Centaurea aggregata* (new host plant), date of collecting: 20.VI.2010, date of exit: 24-27.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Korneyev & White, 2000).

Distribution. England, France, Estonia, Tatarstan, Turkey, North America and Australia (Korneyev & White, 1999) (new record for Iran).

Diagnosis. Wing with 4 black crossbands. Subbasal and discal crossbands and preapical and apical crossbands connected in anterior margin of the wing. Subbasal crossband not extending to posterior margin of the wing (Fig. 4). Mesonotal scutum shining. Aculeus length less than 2 mm and as in Fig. 6.

Fig. 4. *Urophora quadrifasciata quadrifasciata*, wing.***Urophora quadrifasciata sjumorum* (Rohdendorf, 1937)**

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 3 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 17.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Korneyev & White, 1999).

Distribution. Iran: West Azerbaijan and Ardabil (Karimpoor & Merz, 2006; Mohamadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010); Cyprus, Turkey, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, Kirghizia, Israel, Pakistan and China (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & White, 1999).

***Urophora tenuior* Hendel, 1910**

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 3 ♀, Bijar, 2000 m, reared from flower heads of *Cousinia sanandajensis* (new host plant), date of collecting: 21.VII.2009, date of exit: 3.VIII.2009.

Host plants. *Cousinia mollis* (Korneyev & White, 2000).

Distribution. Iran: East Azerbaijan, Khorasan Razavi (Zaitzev, 1947; Gilasian, 2007); Turkmenistan and Afghanistan (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999).

***Urophora tenuis* Becker, 1908* (Figs. 5 & 8)**

Korneyev & White, 1999.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, swept from *Centaurea aggregata*, 20.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Serratula* spp. (Korneyev & White, 1999).

Distribution. Russia, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, China and Mongolia (Korneyev & White, 1999) (new record for Iran).

Diagnosis. This species can be recognized from hyaline wings. First segment of flagellum and femora yellow and notopleural area black. Aculeus with two pairs of steps (Fig. 8) and wing length less than 3.5 mm.

Figs. 6-8. *Urophora* aculeus tip: 6, *U. quadrifasciata quadrifasciata*, 7, *U. cuspidata*, 8, *U. tenuis*.

Tribe Noectini

Hypenidium roborowskii (Becker, 1908)

Hendel, 1927.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Sanandaj, 5km to Ghorveh, Kurdistan province; 1800 m, N: 35°06.575, E: 47°56.613, reared from flower heads of *Lactuca* sp., date of collecting: 30.VII.2009, date of exit: 1.IX.2009.

Host plants. *Lactuca* sp. (Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Tehran (Gilasian, 2007; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a); Syria, Jordan, Iraq, Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Middle Asia, and China (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000).

Tribe Tephritini

Acanthophilus helianthi (Rossi, 1794)

Becker, 1913 (*Trupanea*); Hendel, 1927; Zaitzev, 1947; Foote, 1984; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Merz, 1994.

Material. 1 ♂, Sanandaj, 1400 m, N: 35°16.274, E: 47°01.779, 4.VI.2009; 1 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Mamatkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, reared from flower heads of *Cosmos bipinnatus* (new host plant), date of collecting: 5.VI.2009, date of exit: 17.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 1940 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea amadanensis* (new host plant), date of collecting: 5.VI.2009, date of exit: 17.VI.2009; 3 ♂, 2 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 1940 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea nemecii* (new host plant), date of collecting: 5.VI.2009, date of exit: 12-16.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 1940 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea leuzeoides* (new host plant), date of collecting: 5.VI.2009, date of exit: 10-21.VI.2009; 3 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Dozakh Dareh, 2000 m, N: 35°42.623, E: 46°47.018, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea aucheri* (new host plant), date of collecting: 6.VI.2009, date of exit: 21.VI.2009; 31 ♂, 27 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, reared from flower heads of *Jurinea* sp., date of collecting: 6.VI.2009, date of exit: 12-19.VI.2009; 6 ♂, 12 ♀, Uraman, Marivan, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, 7.VI.2009.

Host plants. The larvae develop in flower heads of *Carthamus* spp. and *Centaurea* spp. (Merz, 1994; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010 a).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, West and East Azerbaijan, Esfahan, Fars, Golestan, Hamedan, Khuzestan, Mazandaran, Sistan & Baluchestan, Tehran, Zanjan (Dirlbek & Dirlbekova, 1974; Gilasian, 2007); Europe, Syria, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Afghanistan, Thailand and Africa (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000; Merz & Dawah, 2005; Merz, 2008).

Campiglossa producta (Loew, 1844)

Hendel, 1927; Zaitzev, 1947; Dirlbek, 1980 (*Paroxyyna tessellata*); Freidberg & Kugler, 1989 (*Paroxyyna*); Norrbom *et al.*, 1999.

Material examined. 1 ♂, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Mamatkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, 4.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 6.VI.2009; 1 ♂, Sanandaj-Marivan road, Jhavroud, 1370 m, N: 35°14.156, E: 45°29.187, 7.VI.2009; 1 ♂, Uraman, Marivan, 2200 m, 7.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Bijar, 2000 m, reared from flower heads of *Lactuca serriola* (new host plant), date of collecting: 20.VII.2009, date of exit: 30.VII.2009; 1 ♂, Sanandaj-Marivan road, Jhavroud, 1370 m, N: 35°14.156, E: 45°29.187, 7.VI.2009; 12 ♂, 1 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Mamatkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, 17.VI.2010; 1 ♂, 2 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 18.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Chondrilla juncea*, *Crepis* spp., *Leontodon* spp., *Hieracium* spp. (Merz, 1994).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Fars, Golestan, Khuzestan, Lorestan,

Tehran, West and East Azerbaijan (Gilasian, 2007; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010 b); N Africa, Canary Is., central and southern Europe, Middle Asia, Israel, Syria, Jordan, Iraq and Afghanistan (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000).

Sphenella marginata (Fallén, 1814)

Freidberg & Kugler, 1989.

Material examined. 1 ♂, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 1940 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, 4.VI.2009; 1 ♂, Marivan, Uraman, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, 7.VI.2009; 2 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 6.VI.2009.

Host plants. *Senecio* spp. (Merz, 1994)

Distribution. Iran: Kurdistan (Mohammadzade Namin & Nozari, in press); Europe, Asian Russia (West Siberia), Egypt, Israel and Afghanistan (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989).

Tephritis formosa (Loew, 1844)

Freidberg & Kugler, 1989.

Material examined. 1 ♂, Saral, Divan Dareh, 50km to Ghorveh, 15.VI.2010.

Host plants. In Europe reared from *Sonchus* spp., *Hypochaeris radicata* and *Crepis virens* (Merz, 1994).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Mazandaran, Tehran (Dirlbek & Dirlbekova, 1974; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a); Europe, except Scandinavia, to Israel (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999).

Tephritis hurvitzii Freidberg, 1981

Hendel, 1927 (*Tephritis recurrens*, pro parte); Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Merz, 1994.

Material examined. 25 ♂, 17 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 24.VIII.2009; 1 ♂, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 1940 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, 17.VI.2010.

Host plants. The larvae develop in stem galls on *Scorzonera syriaca* and *Tragopogon longirostris* (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, West Azerbaijan, Tehran (Gilasian, 2007; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010; Mohammadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a); Greece, Ukraine, Cyprus, Turkey, Israel, Syria, Jordan, Lebanon, Iraq, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan (Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000).

Tephritis mesopotamica Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000*

(Figs. 9, 11 & 12)

Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. Not known.

Distribution. Iraq (Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000); Iran (new record).

Diagnosis. Wing pattern brownish and reticulate. r_1 cell without small hyaline spot in apical brown part. Cell r_1 with two large hyaline spots and 3 hyaline spots in r_{2+3} cell

Fig. 9. *Tephritis mesopotamica*, wing.

posterior of two large hyaline spots of r_1 cell. Brown spot at apex of R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} connected with main spot (Fig. 9). Aculeus shape as in Figs. 11 and 12.

Tephritis postica (Loew, 1844)

Freidberg & Kugler, 1989.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀, Sanandaj, 1400 m, N: 35°16.274, E: 47°01.779, reared from flower heads of *Onopordon acanthium*, date of collecting: 5.VI.2009; date of exit: 15.VI.2009; 1 ♂, Saral, Divan Dareh, 50km to Ghorveh, 15.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Onopordon cynarocephalum* (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989).

Distribution. Iran: Esfahan, Hamedan, Kermanshah, Khorasan Razavi, Semnan, Tehran, Zanjan, Ardabil (Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010); South to North Africa, France, cent. Europe, Ukraine, Israel and Uzbekistan (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Tephritis pulchra (Loew, 1844) (Figs. 10, 13 & 14)

Freidberg & Kutuk, 2002.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. *Scorzonera* spp. (Freidberg & Kutuk, 2002).

Distribution. Cent. & S. Europe to Turkey and North Africa (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999) (new record for Iran).

Diagnosis. Wing pattern blackish and reticulated. r_1 cell with small hyaline spot in apical brown part. Cell r_1 with two large hyaline spots. Hyaline spots in r_{2+3} cell not con-

Fig. 10. *Tephritis pulchra*, wing.

Figs. 11-14. *Tephritis* aculeus: 11-12, *T. mesopotamica*; 13-14, *T. pulchra* (12, 14 - apex, enlarged).

nected to two large hyaline spots of r_1 cell. Brown spot at apex of R_{4+5} and M_{1+2} connected with main spot (Fig. 10). Aculeus tip with one pair of distinct steps (Fig. 14).

Tephritomyia lauta (Loew, 1869)

Dirlbek, 1980.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Matkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, 4.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. Flower heads of *Echinops viscosus* (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil and Tehran (Mohamadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010; Mohamadzade Namin, Nozari & Rasouljan, 2010a); Greece, Israel, Iran, Tunisia and Egypt (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Trupanea amoena (Frauenfeld, 1857)

Hendel, 1927; Zaitzev, 1947; Dirlbek, 1980; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Bijar, 2000 m, reared from flower heads of *Lactuca serriola*, date of collecting: 23.VII.2009, date of exit: 4.VIII.2009; 3 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 24.VIII.2009.

Host plants. *Lactuca* spp., *Picris hieracioides* and *Sonchus* spp. (Merz, 1994).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, East Azerbaijan, Khorasan Jonubi, Sistan va Baluchestan, Tehran (Zaitzev, 1947; Hering, 1956; Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010); Central and southern Europe, Israel, Syria, Iraq, Saudi Arabia and UAE (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Dirlbek, 2000; Merz, 2005; Merz, 2008).

Trupanea stellata (Fuesslin, 1775)

Becker, 1913; Hendel, 1927; Zaitzev, 1947; Dirlbek, 1980; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989.

Material examined. 1 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, 17.VI.2009; 1 ♂, Sanandaj, Little Abidar Mountain, 1950 m, N: 35°17.542, E: 46°57.931, 6.VI.2009; 1 ♀, Sanandaj, Little Abidar Mountain, 1800 m, N: 35°17.495, E: 46°58.179, reared from flower heads of *Senecio vulgaris*, date of collecting: 16.VI.2009; date of exit: 22.VI.2009; 1 ♂, 2 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, reared from flower heads of *Senecio* sp., date of collecting: 8.VI.2009; date of exit: 17.VI.2009.

Host plants. The larvae develop in flower heads of *Anthemis* spp., *Artemisia judaica*, *Aster* sp., *Bidens* sp., *Centaurea* spp., *Crepis* spp., *Inula* spp., *Picris* sp., *Senecio* spp. and *Serratula* sp. (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Merz, 1994).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Kerman, Kermanshah, Sistan va Baluchestan, Tehran, East and West Azerbaijan, (Diribek, 1980; Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010) South to North Africa, Central and southern Europe, Israel, Iraq, Armenia, Saudi Arabia, India and Mongolia (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Diribek, 2000; Merz, 2005).

Tribe Terelliini

Chaetorellia sp. near *australis* Hering, 1940

White & Marquardt, 1989.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 3 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Matkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, 17.VI.2010, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea aucheri*, date of collecting: 17.VI.2010, date of exit: 25.VI.2010.

Remarks. This species is similar to *C. australis* in following characters: anterior supra-alar seta based on yellow ground and discal and preapical crossbands joined in anterior margin of the wing; but aculeus length is more than 2mm and aculeus tip is not as acute as in *C. jaceae*.

Chaetostomella sp. near *cylindrica* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Korneyev, 1986.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 5 ♀, Dezli, Uraman, Marivan, reared from flower heads of *Cousinia* sp., date of collecting: 20.VI.2010, date of exit: 3.VII.2010.

Orellia falcata (Scopoli, 1763)

Korneyev, 2003.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, swept from flower heads of *Tragopogon* sp., 7.VI.2009.

Host plants. *Tragopogon longirostre* (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989).

Distribution. Iran: Markazi, East Azerbaijan (Haji Ghorbani, 2010; Gilasian, 2007) and Tehran (Mohamadzaade Namin, unpublished data); Throughout Europe, Russia, Israel and Central Asia (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Orellia stictica (Gmelin, 1790)

Korneyev, 2003.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Ubato, 2300 m, N: 36°04.592, E: 46°49.660, 7.VI.2009.

Host plants. Larvae in flower heads *Tragopogon* spp. (Valery Korneyev, personal communication)

Distribution. Iran: Golestan, Mazandaran and Tehran (Diribek & Diribekova, 1974; Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a); France, Germany, Bulgaria, Sweden and Ukraine (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Terellia gynaecochroma (Hering, 1937)

Rikhter, 1988; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989 (as *Orellia lappae*).

Material examined. 15 ♂, 9 ♀, Sanandaj-Marivan road, Jhavroud, 1370 m, N: 35°14.156, E: 45°29.187, swept from flower heads of *Onopordon acanthium*, 7.VI.2009; 7 ♂, 4 ♀, Bijar, 2000 m, 8.VI.2009.

Host plants. *Onopordum* spp. (Rikhter, 1988; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989) (as *Orellia lappae*).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Fars, Kurdistan, Qazvin and Tehran (Gi-

lasian, 2007; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010 a); Central and Southern Europe, Cyprus, Israel, Jordan and Syria (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Norrbom *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Diribek, 2000).

Terellia colon (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. 4 ♂, 3 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 2000 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea amadanensis* (new host plant), date of collecting: 5.VI.2009, date of exit: 16.VI.2009; 2 ♂, Uraman, Marivan, 1700 m, N: 35°19.655, E: 46°11.316, 7.VI.2009.

Host plants. *Centaurea* spp. (Rikhter, 1988).

Distribution. Iran: West Azerbaijan (Karimpoor, 2006); North Africa, Britain, Sweden, Russia, Israel and Kazakstan (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Terellia serratulae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Diribek & Diribeková, 1974 (*Terellia longicauda* — misid.); Diribek, 1980; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Korneyev & Diribek, 2000.

Material examined. 3 ♂, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, 2000 m, N: 35°18.107, E: 46°56.488, 16.VI.2009; 2 ♂, Saral, Ghojr, 2110 m, N: 35°45.831, E: 46°58.316, 18.VI.2009.

Host plants. *Carduus* spp., *Cirsium* spp. (Rikhter, 1988; Freidberg & Kugler, 1989; Merz, 1994) and *Carduus onopordioides* (Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil, Gilan, Khorasan, Kohkiluyeh va Boyer Ahmad, Mazandaran, Tehran, West Azerbaijan (Becker, 1913; Gilasian, 2007; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Rasoulilian, 2010a); British Is., Scandinavia and Kazakstan S to N Africa, Israel, Syria and Iraq (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999; Korneyev & Diribek, 2000).

Terellia uncinata White, 1989

White, 1989.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 1 ♀, Saral, Dozakh Dareh, 2000 m, N: 35°42.623, E: 46°47.018, reared from flower heads of *Centaurea solstitialis*, date of collecting: 18.VI.2009, date of exit: 2.VII.2009.

Host plants. *Centaurea nicaeensis* and *C. solstitialis* (White, 1989).

Distribution. Iran: Arak, Ardabil (Haji Ghorbani *et al.*, 2010; Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010); Italy, Albania, Bulgaria, Greece and Turkey (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Terellia zerovae Korneyev, 1985

Korneyev, 1985; White, 1989.

Material examined. 18 ♂, 15 ♀, Sanandaj, Abidar mountain, Matkeh, 1660 m, N: 35°18.819, E: 46°57.281, 17.VI.2010.

Host plants. *Centaurea argentea*, *C. diffusa*, *C. maculosa*, *C. calcitrapa*, *C. iberica*, *C. solstitialis* (White, 1989) and *C. aucheri* (Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010 b).

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil (Mohamadzaade Namin, Nozari & Najarpour, 2010); Romania, Greece, Turkey, Tadzhikistan (Norrbon *et al.*, 1999).

Acknowledgements

We wish to express our sincere thanks to Valery A. Korneyev (Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine) for confirmation of identification of specimens, review of this manuscript and valuable comments. We also thank Hamed Ghobari (University of Kurdistan) for his assistance during fieldwork. We also appreciate corrections and comments made by an anonymous reviewer.

References

- Afshar, J. (1937) Harmful insects of fruit trees in Iran. *Journal of Agricultural Organization*, 1-11.
- Becker, T. (1913) Persische Dipteren von den Expeditionen des Herrn N. Zarudny 1898 und 1901. *Ezheg. Zool. Muz.*, 17: 503-654.
- Behdad, E. (1988) Pests and diseases of jungle and ornamental trees of Iran. Neshat Esfahan press, 1-888.
- Behdad, E. (2003) Introductory entomology and important plant pests in Iran. Neshat Esfahan press, 1-840.
- Dirlbek, J. (1980) Ergebnisse der tschechoslowakischen Expedition des Nationalmuseums in Prag nach Iran (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Acta Universitatis Carolinae Biologica (Prague)*, 269-274.
- Dirlbek, J. & Dirlbekova, O. (1974) Asiatische Bohrfliegenarten in den Sammlungen des Nationalmuseums in Prag und des Mährischen Museums in Brünn. *Folia Facultatis Scientiarum Naturalium Universitatis Purkynianae Brunensis*, 15, 85-90.
- Freidberg, A. & Kugler, J. (1989) Diptera: Tephritidae. *Fauna Palaestina, Insecta*, 4, 1-212 + 8 plates.
- Freidberg, A. & Kutuk, M. (2002) A new species of *Tephritis* from Turkey, with a key to the species of the *Tephritis pulchra* group. *Israel Journal of Zoology*, 48(4), 295-311.
- Gilasian, E. (2007) Insects of Iran: The list of Diptera in the Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum of Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection: Diptera (XXVIII): Tephritidae. *Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection Publication*, 15, 1-23.
- Haji Ghorbani, S., Goldasteh, Sh. & Mohamadzade Namin, S. (2010) The first report of *Terellia uncinata* White, 1989 (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Iran. *Proceedings of 19th Iranian Plant Protection Congress*, 139.
- Haji Ghorbani, S. (2010) Faunistic study of fruit flies (Dip.: Tephritidae) and their host plants in Arak and suburb. Islamic Azad University Arak branch, M. Sc. thesis. 1-122.
- Hendel, F. G. (1927) 49. Trypetidae. In: Lindner, E., ed. *Die Fliegen der palaearktischen Region*, Vol. 5, Stuttgart, 1-221 + 17 plates.
- Karimpoor, Y. & Merz B. (2006) The first report of *Urophora quadrifaciata* and *Urophora xanthippe* (Dip. Tephritidae) from Iran. *Proceedings of the 17th Iranian plant protection congress*, 73.
- Korneyev, V. A. (2003) New and little-known Tephritidae (Diptera, Cyclorrhapha) from Europe. *Vestnik zoologii*, 37(3), 3-12.
- Korneyev, V. A. & Merz B. (1997) A new species of *Rhagoletis* Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae), with notes on Central Asian species. *Journal of Ukrainian Entomological Society*, 55-64.
- Korneyev, V. A. & Dirlbek J. (2000) The fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of Syria, Jordan and Iraq. *Studia dipterologica*, 7(2), 463-482.
- Korneyev, V. A. & White I. M. (1999) Tephritids of the genus *Urophora* R.-D. (Diptera, Tephritidae) of East Palaearctic: III. Key to palaearctic species. *Entomological Review*, 79 (3), 464-482.
- Korneyev, V. A. & White I. M. (2000) Tephritids of the genus *Urophora* R.-D. (Diptera, Tephritidae) of East Palaearctic: IV. Conclusion. *Entomological Review*, 80, 497-510.
- Merz, B. (1994) *Diptera: Tephritidae*. Insecta Helvetica Fauna, HGE press, Geneva, 10, 1-198.
- Merz, B. & Dawah, A. (2005) Fruit flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) from Saudi Arabia, with descriptions of a new genus and six new species. *Revue Suisse De Zoologie*, 112 (4), 983-1028.
- Merz, B. (2008) Order Diptera, family Tephritidae. In: Van Harten, A., ed. *Arthropod fauna of the UAE*, Dar Al Ummah Printing Publishing, Distribution & Advertising, Abu Dhabi, 643-661.
- Mohamadzade Namin, S. & Nozari, J. (2011) The first report of two new genera of the subfamily Tephritinae (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Iran. *Journal of Iranian Entomological Society*, in press.
- Mohamadzade Namin, S., Nozari, J. & Najarpour, A. (2010) The fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) in the fauna of Ardabil province, with new records for Iran. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 1(3), 35-41.
- Mohamadzade Namin, S., Nozari, J. & Najarpour, A. (2011) A new species of *Terellia* (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Iran with a key to the species of the *tarbinskiorum* group. *Zootaxa*, 2750, 65-68.
- Mohamadzade Namin, S., Nozari, J. & Rasouljan, G. (2010a) The fruit flies (Diptera, Tephritidae) in Tehran province, with new records for Iranian fauna. *Vestnik zoologii*, 44(1), 23-34.
- Mohamadzade Namin, S., Nozari, J. & Rasouljan, G. (2010b). The first report of *Goniurellia persignata* Freidberg, 1980 (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Iran. *Proceedings of 19th Iranian Plant Protection Congress*, 138.
- Norrbom, A. L., Carroll, L. E., Thompson, F. C., White, I. M. & Freidberg, A. (1999) Systematic Database of Names. In: Thompson, F. C., ed. *Fruit Fly Expert Identification System and Systematic Information Database*, Myia, 65-299.
- Parchami Araghi, M. (1995) Introduce of *Dacus ciliatus* Loew (Dip.: Tephritidae) from Iran. *Proceedings of the 12th Iranian plant protection congress*, 160-161.
- Richter, V. A. (1988) Family Tephritidae (Trypetidae) — fruit flies. In: Bei-Bienko, G. Ya., ed. *Keys to the insects of the European part of the USSR. Vol. V. Diptera, Siphonaptera. Part 2*, Leiden, New York, 212-276.
- White, I. M. (1988) *Tephritid flies (Diptera: Tephritidae)*. Handbooks for identification on British insects, CAB International, London, 1-134.
- White, I. M. (1989) A new species of *Terellia* Robineau-Desvoidy associated with *Centaurea solstitialis* L. and a revision of the *Terellia virens* Loew species group (Diptera: Tephritidae). *CAB international Institute of Entomology*, 125, 53-61.
- White, I. M. & Marquardt, K. (1989) A revision of the genus *Chaetorellia* Hendel (Diptera: Tephritidae) including a new species associated with spotted knapweed, *Centaurea maculosa* Lam. (Asteraceae). *Bull. Ent. Res.*, 79, 453-487.
- White, I. M. & Elson-Harris, M. M. (1992) *Fruit Flies of Economic Significance: Their Identification and Bionomics*. CAB International and ACIAR, London, 1-601.
- Zaitzev, F. A. (1947) The fruit fly fauna of the Caucasus and adjacent lands (Diptera, Trypetidae). *Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta Akademii Nauk Gruzinskoy SSR*, 7, 1-16.